

A

- 2019 • Dec. The first report of COVID-19 in Wuhan
- 2020 • Feb. Identification of SARS-CoV-2
- Mar. Declaration of a global pandemic by the WHO
- 2021 • Feb. - 1st dose
- Mar. - 2nd dose
- Dec. - 3rd dose
- Wuhan (monovalent)
- 2022 • May - 4th dose
- Oct. - 5th dose
- Wuhan-BA.1 (bivalent)
- 2023 • ~May - 6th dose
- ~Sep. - 7th dose
- Wuhan-BA.4/5 (bivalent)
- XBB.1.5 (monovalent)
- 2024 • Oct. - 8th dose
- JN.1 (monovalent)
- self-amplifying mRNA vaccine

2024 Dec. Disclosure request project started

B

C

Figure 1

A

The Yukoku Union + United Citizens for Stopping mRNA Vaccines

The COVID-19 Vaccination Data Disclosure Request Project

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Deaths Mortality Short-Term Mortality Lot Number Search : e.g.: EX3616 *Partial lot nam Search

Data Last Updated on :October 12, 2025
Data collection period : Feb 1st, 2021 - May 1st, 2025

B

Prefectures : Time from vaccination to death :

	Young (up to 19)		Working-Age (20 to 69)		Senior (70 and above)		Total	
	Deaths	Doses	Deaths	Doses	Deaths	Doses	Deaths	Doses
Total for all lots	218	1,085,369	24,203	9,831,822	196,593	6,730,321	221,014	17,647,512

C

Lot Name	Young (up to 19)			Working-Age (20 to 69)			Senior (70 and above)			Total		
	Deaths	Doses	Mortality(%)	Deaths	Doses	Mortality(%)	Deaths	Doses	Mortality(%)	Deaths	Doses	Mortality(%)
HG5938	0	0	0.00	0	2	0.00	10	12	83.33	10	14	71.429
FM8584	0	0	0.00	0	3	0.00	2	3	66.67	2	6	33.333
GJ2676	0	0	0.00	0	1	0.00	2	5	40.00	2	6	33.333
4000195A	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	2	8	25.00	2	8	25.000
Nuvaxovid	0	0	0.00	1	1	100.00	1	7	14.29	2	8	25.000
710002A	0	1	0.00	2	102	1.96	86	257	33.46	88	360	24.444
GJ9568	0	0	0.00	0	6	0.00	3	9	33.33	3	15	20.000
FL9605	0	0	0.00	1	8	12.50	1	2	50.00	2	10	20.000
EY5765	0	0	0.00	0	7	0.00	4	17	23.53	4	24	16.667
HG2354	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	1	6	16.67	1	6	16.667

D

Lot Name	Young (up to 19)			Working-Age (20 to 69)			Senior (70 and above)			Total		
	Deaths	Doses	Mortality(%)	Deaths	Doses	Mortality(%)	Deaths	Doses	Mortality(%)	Deaths	Doses	Mortality(%)
HG2273	0	1,641	0.00	354	65,952	0.54	6,429	124,676	5.16	6,783	192,269	3.528
HG2346	0	1,752	0.00	385	68,188	0.56	5,185	104,294	4.97	5,570	174,234	3.197
HG2352	1	2,413	0.04	399	73,888	0.54	5,140	101,365	5.07	5,540	177,666	3.118
HG2251	0	998	0.00	303	56,872	0.53	5,173	113,562	4.56	5,476	171,432	3.194
GJ7140	3	9,853	0.03	534	113,917	0.47	4,567	119,402	3.82	5,104	243,172	2.099
HH1299	0	2,886	0.00	274	59,689	0.46	4,153	64,761	6.41	4,427	127,336	3.477
HG2348	1	3,057	0.03	291	61,191	0.48	3,823	64,931	5.89	4,115	129,179	3.186
FL1839	3	15,235	0.02	305	103,532	0.29	3,705	129,676	2.86	4,013	248,443	1.615
GJ2675	1	8,704	0.01	415	110,759	0.37	3,496	111,451	3.14	3,912	230,914	1.694
GJ1842	3	8,448	0.04	389	110,809	0.35	3,399	110,603	3.07	3,791	229,860	1.649

E

Figure 2

Figure 3

A**Figure 4**

Figure 5

A

B

Figure 6

Table 1. Standardization using Japan's vaccinated population

Dose	Vaccinated	Japanese vaccine recipients	Normalization value	Estimated Japanese vaccine recipients	Estimated final dose	Ratio of final dose
1st	4,025,948	104,761,469 ^{a, b}	26.0		1,288,193	1.2%
2nd	4,004,076	103,473,276 ^b	25.8		16,772,468	16.0%
3rd	3,406,171	86,700,808 ^b	25.5		22,929,105	21.9%
4th	2,474,406		25.8 ± 0.29	63,771,703 ± 717,747	20,526,712	19.6%
5th	1,677,949		25.8 ± 0.29	43,244,991 ± 486,720	14,523,207	13.9%
6th	1,114,434		25.8 ± 0.29	28,721,784 ± 323,262	8,541,042	8.2%
7th	783,033		25.8 ± 0.29	20,180,741 ± 227,133	18,643,539	17.8%
8th	59,645		25.8 ± 0.29	1,537,203 ± 17,301	1,537,203	1.5%
total	17,545,662				104,761,469	100.0%

a. This number of first-dose recipients was considered to be the total number of COVID-19 vaccine recipients in Japan.

b. These numbers are based on the Ministry of Health, Labour and Welfare's announcement dated 31 March 2024.